

ISic0435

Funerary inscription for Marcus Lus[-?] Silvan[us]

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

'Syracusic inventa in feudo Carancino in vinea soc. Iesu.' (CIL ad loc.)

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa (?)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. M(arcus) · Lus[---]

2. Silvan[us---]

3. vix(it) · ann[os ---]

Apparatus

Text of CIL

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491663

EDCS 21900497

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus*

Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum. Berlin. At 10.7155 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650768>)

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